

1 **Climatic variability over the last 3000 years in the central - western Mediterranean Sea**
2 **(Menorca Basin) detected by planktonic foraminifera and stable isotope records**

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15

16 **Abstract**

17 The climate evolution of the last 2700 years in the central - western Mediterranean Sea has been
18 reconstructed from marine sediment records by integrating planktonic foraminifera and geochemical
19 signals. The results provide the characterization of six climatic phases: Balearic Bronze Age (BA),
20 Roman Period (RP), Dark Age (DA), Medieval Climate Anomaly (MCA), Little Ice Age (LIA) and
21 Industrial Period (IP). Paleoclimatic curve inferred from planktonic foraminifera associated with
22 heavy values in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ *Globigerinoides ruber* during the BA document two cold intervals (spanning
23 ca. 200 years) related to the Homeric and Greek solar minima. The dominance of *Turborotalita*
24 *quinqueloba* –*Globigerinita glutinata* gr. and *Globigerina bulloides* during the RP suggest high
25 fertility surface waters condition probably triggered by the increase in precipitation. During the DA,
26 changes in the foraminiferal paleoclimate curve and oxygen isotope values display a cold –dry phase
27 from 700 CE to the end of the DA (ca. 850 CE). This phase corresponds to the cold Roman IV solar

28 minimum and marks the beginning of a long - term cooling interval that terminates during the LIA.
29 The MCA is characterized by mild climatic conditions, interrupted at ca. 1050 CE by a cold - dry
30 event. The gradually increase in abundance of *G. ruber* white characterize the IP warm period.
31 The reconstructed climate evolution in the Balearic Basin results almost time - equivalent with the
32 Mediterranean climate variability over the last 2700 years.

33

34 **Keywords**

35 Paleoclimate, Balearic Sea, fossil records, historical climate change, last three millennia.

36

37 **1. Introduction**

38 The study of last three millennia climate variability are crucial to distinguish anthropogenic from
39 natural forcing and to provide information for medium and long - term prediction models. These
40 reconstructions can be obtained using high-quality datasets of proxies measured from different natural
41 archives. This background condition provides important information allowing to document
42 considerable climate oscillations that played an important role in social reorganizations in Europe.
43 However, our understanding of the magnitude and spatial extent as well as the possible causes and
44 concurrences of climate changes are still limited and the scarcity of integrated information from
45 marine records emerges (PAGES, 2009; Lionello, 2012; Luterbacher et al., 2012).

46 The Mediterranean area is considered one of the most responsive regions to global change and is an
47 ideal archive to investigate paleoclimate oscillation at secular scale because of its high-sedimentation
48 rate marine records, paleo-latitudinal and land locked configuration (e.g., Cacho et al., 1999; Rohling,
49 2001; Martrat et al., 2004; Frigola et al., 2007; Taricco et al., 2009; Nieto-Moreno et al., 2011; Lirer
50 et al., 2013). Most of the current high-resolution studies are still limited to continental shelf areas
51 (e.g., Oldfield et al., 2003; Piva et al., 2008; Lirer et al., 2014; Grauel et al., 2013; Di Bella et al.,
52 2014; Jalali et al., 2015; Taricco et al., 2015; Bonomo et al., 2016; Margaritelli et al., 2016; Sicre et

53 al., 2016; Di Rita et al., 2018) and, in contrast, little is know about deep marine records (Nieto-Moreno
54 et al., 2011; 2013a, 2013b; Cisneros et al., 2016; Gogou et al., 2016).

55 Planktonic Foraminifera are the most common proxy used for late Pleistocene-Holocene
56 paleoclimatic reconstructions (e.g., Capotondi et al., 1999; Sprovieri et al., 2003; Tedesco and
57 Thunell 2003; Amore et al., 2004; Bárcena et al., 2004; Sbaffi et al., 2004; King and Howard 2004;
58 Hald et al., 2007; Fislser and Hendy, 2008; Piva et al., 2008; Moreno et al., 2012; Di Bella et al., 2014;
59 Lirer et al., 2013, 2014; Munz et al., 2015; Margaritelli et al., 2016). Similarly, the oxygen isotope
60 geochemistry of foraminifera is a well-established paleoceanographic tool (e.g., Emiliani, 1955;
61 Shackleton, 1967) because of the oxygen in foraminiferal calcite derives from the seawater in which
62 the organism lived. Hence, the isotope ratios can provide information about the composition and
63 history of that water, and the environmental and climatic conditions in which the test was secreted
64 (e.g., Capotondi et al., 1999; Schilman et al., 2001; Rohling et al., 2004; Piva et al., 2008; Nieto
65 Moreno et al., 2011; Pearson, 2012; Grauel et al., 2013; Lirer et al., 2013, 2014; Cisneros et al., 2016).
66 In this work, we contribute to evidence the climate phases over the last 2700 in central-western
67 Mediterranean (Catalan - Balearic Sea) and their link with the historical / cultural periods. We
68 specifically address this issue by presenting an integrated study performed on planktonic foraminifera
69 and stable isotopic record. In addition, we provide the comparison between different areas of the
70 Mediterranean region in order to verify the synchronicity of the climate phases. This effort provide a
71 more comprehensive picture of the climate changes in the Mediterranean region.

72

73 **2. Oceanographic settings of the study area**

74 The Balearic Sea is a sub-basin of the Western Mediterranean, located between the Iberian Peninsula
75 and the Balearic Islands; it is commonly considered a key transition region between the Gulf of Lions
76 and the Algerian basin (Pinot et al., 1995). The surface hydrological pattern in this area is dominated
77 by the Modified Atlantic Water, which originates from the inflowing Atlantic Water and is
78 progressively modified by air-sea interaction and mixing along its path through the basin (Send et al.,

79 1999). At the studied location, this Modified Atlantic Water arrives through the Balearic Current (Fig.
80 1), which flows northwards across the Balearic Sea after separating from the Northern Current that
81 previously bathes the Gulf of Lions and the Catalan coast (Montserrat et al., 2008; Lòpez-García et al.,
82 1994). The Gulf of Lions is the region where the Western Mediterranean Deep Water forms almost
83 each winter by deep convection offshore mostly driven by the occurrence of persistent cold, dry and
84 persistent N-NW winds that trigger heat and buoyancy loss of offshore waters (MEDOC, 1970;
85 Schroeder et al., 2010). In the convection process of this deep water mass also contributes the
86 intermediate water masses, mostly Levantine Intermediate Waters formed in the Eastern
87 Mediterranean Sea and enters into the Western Mediterranean through the Strait of Sicily (Pinardi
88 and Masetti, 2000). Both Western Mediterranean Deep Water and particularly Levantine Intermediate
89 Water masses form the water outflow that exits the Mediterranean through the Strait of Gibraltar
90 (Milot, 1990; Lionello et al., 2006).

91 The Strait of Gibraltar plays a crucial role for the environment of the Mediterranean Sea; the fluxes
92 through the strait compensate for the mass deficit due to the large evaporation in the basin, supply
93 comparatively low-salinity water-masses to one of the saltiest seas on Earth, and also provide a small
94 supply of heat, because the Mediterranean Outflow Water is cooler than the Atlantic Water inflow
95 (i.e., Lionello, 2012; Schroeder et al., 2012; Malanotte-Rizzoli et al., 2014).

96

97 **3. Material and methods**

98 *3.1 Core description and chronology*

99 This study focus on composite multicore HER-MC-MR3.1A/3.3 recovered at 2117 m water
100 depth in 2009 during HERMESIONE expedition on board the R/V Hespérides (for details see
101 Cisneros et al., 2016) in the Menorca basin (Fig. 1).

102 The correlation between the two investigated cores HER-MC-MR3.1A and HER-MC-MR3.3, as
103 reported in the Figure S2 of the supplementary material in Cisneros et al. (2016), is based on the
104 occurrence of left coiled *G. truncatulinooides* bio - event dated at 1718 ± 10 year Common Era (CE)

105 (Lirer et al. 2013, 2014; Margaritelli et al. 2016). This bio-vent integrated with ^{210}Pb profile, AMS ^{14}C ,
106 software-simulations, SST-tuning, geochemical chronostratigraphy and the top acme of *G.*
107 *quadrilobatus* (Tab. 1) allowed to produce a high-resolution chronology (see for more details the
108 Supplementary Material in Cisneros et al., 2016).

109 The sedimentary sequence consist on by brown - orange nannofossil and foraminiferal silty clay,
110 slightly bioturbated with the presence of enriched layers in pteropods and gastropods fragments and
111 some dark layers (Cisneros et al., 2016). The composite study core is 27 cm length and it was sampled
112 at 0.5 cm resolution from top core to 15 cm below sea level and at 1 cm resolution back to the base
113 of the core. The time interval considered in this study core spans from 702 year Before Common Era
114 (BCE) to 1875 Common Era (CE).

115

116 3.2 Oxygen stable isotopes

117 Oxygen isotope analyses were performed on 15 specimens of *G. ruber* white from the size
118 fraction $> 125 \mu\text{m}$. The measurements were performed at the geochemistry laboratory of the IAMC -
119 CNR (Naples, Italy) with an automated continuous flow carbonate preparation Gas BenchII device
120 (Spötl and Vennemann, 2003) and a ThermoElectron Delta Plus XP mass spectrometer. Acidification
121 of samples was performed at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Every 6 samples, an internal standard (Carrara Marble with $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
122 $= -2.43 \text{ } \text{‰}$ versus VPDB) was run and after 30 samples the NBS19 international standard was
123 measured ($- 2.20 \text{ } \text{‰}$ VPDB). Standard deviations of oxygen isotope measures were estimated at +
124 $0.1 \text{ } \text{‰}$.

125 Oxygen isotope analyses on *G. bulloides* (from a size range of $250 - 355 \mu\text{m}$) were published in
126 Cisneros et al (2016). All the isotope data are reported in $\delta \text{ } \text{‰}$ versus VPDB.

127

128 3.3 Planktonic foraminifera

129 The study of planktonic foraminiferal assemblage was made on 47 samples washed over a 63
130 μm sieve to remove the clay and silt fractions. Quantitative planktonic foraminiferal analyses were

131 carried out on the size fraction > 125 μm , considering at least 300 specimens, a number statistically
132 consistent to perform paleoclimatic reconstructions (see Supplementary material).

133 Some planktonic species have been grouped as follows: *Orbulina* spp. includes both *O. universa* and
134 *O. suturalis*; *Globigerinoides quadrilobatus* includes *G. trilobus* and *G. sacculifer*; *G. ruber* includes
135 *G. gomitulus*; *G. bulloides* includes *G. falconensis*; *Globigerinatella siphonifera* includes *G. calida*.

136 Analyses discriminated between left and right coiling of *G. truncatulinoides* and *G. inflata*.

137 The planktonic foraminiferal paleoclimate curve was constructed following Cita et al. (1977),
138 Sanvoisin et al. (1993), Sprovieri et al., (2006) and Capotondi et al. (2016). It represents the algebraic
139 sum of warm water species percentages (expressed as positive values) and cold water species
140 percentages (expressed as negative values) based on ecological preferences and modern habitat
141 characteristics reported in Hemleben et al. (1989), Rohling et al. (1993), and Pujol and Vergnaud-
142 Grazzini (1995). Warm water species are *G. ruber* (white and pink varieties), *G. quadrilobatus*, *G.*
143 *sacculifer*, *G. siphonifera* and *O. universa*. The cold - water species are *G. bulloides*, *G. glutinata*, *T.*
144 *quiqueloba*, *G. inflata*, *G. truncatulinoides* left coiled and *N. pachyderma* right coiled. Negative and
145 positive values of the curve correspond to the cold and warm surface water, respectively. In order to
146 reconstruct paleoclimatic conditions, the relative abundance of the species or groups are plotted in
147 percentages with respect to the total foraminiferal assemblage vs time. In addition, *G. glutinata* and
148 *T. quiqueloba* are summed together (*T. quiqueloba* - *G. glutinata* gr.) as a proxy of the productivity
149 in the sub - surface waters (Cita et al., 1977; Corselli et al., 2002; Geraga et al., 2008; Jonkers et al.,
150 2010). *N. pachyderma* right coiled and *N. duteretrei* are summed together as a signal of cold water
151 conditions.

152 Cold climate events documented in the planktonic foraminiferal paleoclimatic curve are visually
153 compared with the chronology of solar minima events recorded in the $\Delta^{14}\text{C}$ anomalies (Stuiver et al.,
154 1998), according to the nomenclature of Eddy (1977).

155 For paleoclimate reconstruction and interpretation, we adopt the ecological requirements detected by
156 living planktonic foraminiferal distribution records (De Castro Coppa et al., 1980; Pujol and

157 Vergnaud Grazzini, 1995; Mallo et al., 2017) and in the Gulf of Lions sediment trap data (Rigual-
158 Hernández et al., 2012).

159

160 **4. Results**

161 *4.1 Oxygen stable isotopes*

162 Generally, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. ruber}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ records show a similar pattern over the last 2350
163 yrs; the only opposite pattern are detected at ca. 1050 CE and in the uppermost last 200 yrs (Fig. 2).
164 In detail, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signals show gentle shift vs more positive values from base core to ca. 800 CE (Fig.
165 2). Only $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ signal at ca. 50 CE displays a shift vs lower values (Fig. 2). Upwards, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.}$
166 *ruber* and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ signals document a long standing progressive change to higher values (from –
167 0.84 to + 0.85 ‰ VPDB and from + 1.2 to + 1.5 ‰ VPDB, respectively) superimposed to five higher
168 shifts centred at ca. 750 CE, 1000 CE, 1225 CE, 1500 CE and 1740 CE (Fig. 2).

169

170 *4.2 Planktonic foraminifera*

171 The planktonic foraminiferal specimens are abundant and well preserved. *G. bulloides* and *G.*
172 *ruber* white variety are continuously present (mean values ca. 15 %) in the whole study interval; only
173 from ca. 1700 CE they show a drastic reduction in percentages (Fig. 2). *G. inflata*, *G. truncatulinoides*
174 and *Orbulina* spp. exhibit from ca. 50 CE upwards a decreasing trends followed by peaks in
175 abundance from ca. 800 CE to top core (Fig. 2). Conversely, *T. quinqueloba* and *G. glutinata* increase
176 from ca. 50 CE upwards reaching higher values from ca. 1750 CE to top core (Fig. 2).
177 *G. quadrilobatus* shows low abundance from base core to ca. 50 CE and becomes relevant (about 9
178 %) at ca. 600 CE (Fig. 2). This species shows a progressive upward decreasing trend from 9% to 2%
179 (Fig. 2). *G. ruber* pink variety shows a similar distribution pattern observed for *G. quadrilobatus* gr.
180 (Fig. 2). *G. siphonifera* is constantly present (mean values of ca. 5 %) in the study record with an
181 increase (mean values of ca. 10 %) in the interval from 257 BCE to 118 CE (Fig. 2) and at 882 CE
182 (14.6 %), at 1235 CE (10.6 %), at 1357 CE (13.6 %), at 1627 CE (11.3 %) and at 1764 CE (11.6 %)

183 (Fig. 2). Neogloboquadrinids occur from base core to ca. 1000 CE with low values (from 1 to 9 %)
184 (Fig. 2) and are significant at ca. 1250 CE (ca. 16 %) and from ca. 1750 CE to the top of the core
185 (from 4 to 13 %) (Fig. 2).

186

187 **5. Discussion**

188 *5.1 Paleoclimate reconstruction*

189 The planktonic foraminiferal paleoclimate curve and stable isotopic signals were compared to
190 document the past climate oscillations over the last 2700 yr in the Menorca basin. The principal
191 changes observed in the studied records correspond to the historical climatic phases defined in
192 literature, which match to the major cultural and social reorganization of the Mediterranean region
193 with a consequent anthropogenic control on the marine ecosystems (i.e. Nieto-Moreno et al., 2011,
194 2013a, 2013b; Moreno et al., 2012; Lirer et al., 2013, 2014; Margaritelli et al., 2016).

195 Six climatic phases are defined in the records: Balearic Bronze Age (base core – 50 BCE); Roman
196 Period (50 BCE – 500 CE); Dark Age (500 CE – 850 CE); Medieval Climate Anomaly (850 CE -
197 1200 CE); Little Ice Age (1200 CE – 1825 CE); Industrial Period (1825 CE – top core).

198

199 *5.1.1 Balearic Bronze Age*

200 The oldest interval is the Balearic Bronze Age which approximately corresponding to the
201 archaeological Talayotic Period in Menorca Island and to the Iron Age in other geographic areas.
202 Both the planktonic foraminiferal paleoclimatic and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ curves display two cold climatic
203 events during this period separated by a 200 yr warm phase (Fig. 2). The parallel increase in *G.*
204 *bulloides* and *G. inflata* at ca. 550 BCE and at ca. 250 BCE (Fig. 2) reflects the sediment trap data of
205 Gulf of Lions (Rigual-Hernández et al., 2012) and the living planktonic foraminiferal assemblage in
206 the western Mediterranean Sea during winter season (De Castro Coppa et al., 1980; Pujol and
207 Vergnaud Grazzini, 1995). In detail, the increase in abundance of *G. truncatulinoides* at 550 BCE
208 documents winter deep mixing conditions (Pujol and Vergnaud Grazzini, 1995; Rigual-Hernández et

209 al., 2012), conversely the occurrence of *Neogloboquadrinids* spp. at 250 BCE, suggests lower
210 temperature (Pujol and Vergnaud Grazzini, 1995) and a nutrient supply (Rigual-Hernández et al.,
211 2012). These two cold events approximate the Homeric and Greek solar minima events (Eddy 1977;
212 Stuiver et al., 1998). The climate deterioration at the time of the Greek solar minima is consistent
213 with heavy values in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ signal and with increase in planktonic foraminiferal cool water species
214 (*G. scitula* and *N. pachyderma*) described in the central Tyrrhenian Sea (Margaritelli et al., 2016). In
215 addition, this interval is equivalent in time with a cold phase between 350 and 100 BCE reported by
216 historical source data for the central Italy (Lamb, 1977).

217 The 200 yr warm interval (500 - 300 BCE) is dominated by warm water indicators such as *G. ruber*
218 (white and pink variety), *Orbulina* spp., *G. siphonifera* and *G. quadrilobatus* gr. and also relatively
219 light values of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ (Fig. 2). Continental records from southern Spain indicate a progressive
220 decrease of arid conditions along the Balearic Bronze Age (Martín-Puertas et al., 2008) coincident
221 with the description of other regions of the western Mediterranean (Piva et al., 2008; Lirer et al.,
222 2013). The end of this Balearic Bronze climatic phase, at 50 BCE, is concomitant with the end of the
223 Talayotic historical Period when Menorca became part of the Roman Empire from 123 BCE (De Cet
224 et al., 2012).

225

226 5.1.2 Roman Period

227 The Roman Period starts with a prominent change in the planktonic foraminiferal paleoclimatic
228 curve from warm to cooler conditions at ca. 50 BCE (Fig. 2). The Roman Period is generally
229 characterised by three sudden cooling events (Lirer et al., 2014; Margaritelli et al., 2016). In the study
230 core, the two strong peaks in abundance of *G. inflata*, centred at ca. 50 CE and ca. 250 CE,
231 chronologically correspond to the cold pulses associated to Roman I and to Roman II solar minima
232 (Fig. 2). This interpretation is supported by the occurrence of the maximum relative abundance of *G.*
233 *inflata* during winter in both the sediment trap record of Gulf of Lions (Rigual-Hernández et al., 2012)
234 and in the living planktonic foraminiferal assemblage of central - east Tyrrhenian Sea (De Castro

235 Coppa et al., 1980). *G. inflata* is considered a deep dwelling species (Hemleben et al., 1989;
236 Hemleben et al., 1985) and has been used as an indicator of a cool, deep, homogenous and relatively
237 eutrophic winter mixed layer in the Mediterranean (Rohling et al., 1995; Pérez-Folgado et al., 2003).
238 During these two cooling events, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ signal does not show heavier values (Fig. 2), this may
239 suggest that the intense winter mixing could be more episodic.

240 The paleoclimatic curve documents warm climate condition, at ca. 150 CE, between Roman I and II
241 cold pulses. The planktonic foraminiferal assemblages during this warm phase is characterised by the
242 increase in abundance of *G. ruber* white and *G. siphonifera* associated with *T. quinqueloba* - *G.*
243 *glutinata* gr. and *G. bulloides* (Fig. 2), suggesting relatively warm climate condition during spring/fall
244 associated with high fertility surface waters (Pujol and Vergnaud Grazzini, 1995; Rigual-Hernández
245 et al., 2012). These conditions are in agreement with western Alboran paleoclimatic reconstruction
246 where an increase in precipitation could produce an increase of continental river input inducing sea
247 surface fertility (Martín-Puertas et al., 2010). In the uppermost part of the RP, the paleoclimatic curve
248 highlights a progressive shift vs warm climate condition that exhibit the maximum expression at the
249 base of the following Dark Age (Fig. 2).

250

251 5.1.3 Dark Age

252 The onset of Dark Age is identified at ca. 500 CE associated to a change in the paleoclimatic
253 curve trend (Fig. 2). The paleoclimatic curve and the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. ruber}$ signal show two distinct climatic
254 phases (Fig. 2), in agreement with data reported in the south and central Tyrrhenian Sea (Lirer et al.,
255 2014; Margaritelli et al., 2016). During all the DA, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. ruber}$ values are generally lighter and
256 trends to higher values have been observed at the end of the period (Fig. 2).

257 The first one occurs between ca. 500 and ~ 700 CE and is characterized by $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. ruber}$ light values and
258 the increase in abundance of *G. quadrilobatus* gr., *G. ruber* and *Orbulina* spp. (Fig. 2). These species
259 exhibit their maximum relative abundance values during the stratification period, suggesting summer
260 and fall climate conditions (Pujol and Vergnaud Grazzini, 1995; Rigual-Hernández et al., 2012; Mallo

261 et al., 2017). In contrast, the occurrence of *Neogloboquadrinids* spp. and *G. truncatulinoides* during
262 the onset of the DA (500 - 600 CE), could suggest the intense vertical mixing during winter and the
263 subsequent high food availability in surface waters in winter and spring lead to the proliferation of
264 these species (Rigual-Hernández et al., 2012).

265 The second climate phase chronologically corresponds to the cold Roman IV solar minimum (Fig.
266 2). This interval is characterized by high percentages of *G. inflata* and *Neogloboquadrinids* spp.,
267 suggesting cold climate conditions during winter season (Pujol and Vergnaud Grazzini, 1995; Rigual-
268 Hernández et al., 2012). The concomitant increase in abundance of *T. quinqueloba* - *G. glutinata* gr.
269 (Fig. 2), suggests relatively warm climate conditions during spring/fall associated with high fertility
270 surface waters (Rigual-Hernández et al., 2012). This feature fits with the similar micropaleontological
271 content described by Margaritelli et al. (2016) in the central Tyrrhenian Sea.

272

273 5.1.4 Medieval Climate Anomaly

274 The boundary between the Dark Age and Medieval Climate Anomaly is characterised by the
275 establishment of mild climate condition documented by light values in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. ruber}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$
276 signals (Fig. 2). This climatic signature agrees with others reconstructions performed in the
277 Mediterranean region (i.e. Lamb, 1977; Jones et al., 2004; Mann et al., 2009; Büntgen et al., 2011;
278 Margaritelli et al., 2016). Within this overall mild climatic conditions, at ca. 1000 - 1050 CE, the
279 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. ruber}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ signals show a short - term cooling event [Medieval Cold Event (MCE)].
280 During this period, *T. quinqueloba* - *G. glutinata* gr. increase in abundance (Fig. 2), suggesting an
281 increase in sea surface productivity (Moreno et al., 2012; Gogou et al., 2016).

282 In the uppermost part of the MCA (from 1150 CE to 1200 CE), high frequencies of warm waters
283 species *G. ruber* white variety, *G. ruber* pink variety, *G. quadrilobatus* gr., *Orbulina* spp. with
284 concomitant decrease in abundance of *T. quinqueloba* - *G. glutinata* gr., reflect warmest climate
285 conditions during summer/fall (Rigual-Hernandez et al., 2012). This short - term warm event
286 [Medieval Warm Event (MWE)] has been previously detected in the Tyrrhenian Sea (Lirer et al.,

287 2014; Margaritelli et al., 2016) suggesting that this event is almost synchronous in the western
288 Mediterranean area.

289

290 5.1.5 Little Ice Age

291 The Little Ice Age starts at ca. 1200 CE and based on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ signal and the planktonic
292 foraminiferal paleoclimatic curve, it results characterized by three climatic oscillations: Wolf, Spörer
293 and Maunder cold events, as already evidenced in other sites of the Tyrrhenian Sea (Fig. 2) (Lirer et
294 al., 2014; Margaritelli et al., 2016). All the LIA solar minima are characterized by high abundance
295 percentages of *G. inflata* (Fig. 2) suggesting cold climate condition during winter (Rigual-Hernández
296 et al., 2012). This species is generally considered a deep dwelling species (Hemleben et al., 1985,
297 1989; Rohling et al., 1995; Pérez-Folgado et al., 2003) but the positive phase relation with solar
298 minima could support the strength of this species as a temperature signal. Moreover, these solar
299 minima are characterized also by an increase in abundances of *G. truncatulinoides* (Fig. 2). The
300 abundance pattern of *G. truncatulinoides* is an interesting foraminiferal signal already documented in
301 the Tyrrhenian Sea (Lirer et al., 2013, 2014; Margaritelli et al., 2016) during the Maunder event. In
302 the sediment trap data from Gulf of Lions, Rigual-Hernández et al. (2012) suggest that the elevated
303 abundances of this species, during the winter–spring transition, could be indicate an affinity of this
304 taxon with the increase mixing conditions in the Gulf of Lions. The break - down of the thermocline
305 during winter, the vertical mixing could facilitate the ascent of *G. truncatulinoides* to the euphotic
306 zone, where it reproduces and proliferates due to the increased primary productivity (Hemleben et
307 al., 1985; Schiebel and Hemleben, 2005; Schiebel et al., 2002).

308 Margaritelli et al. (2016) linked the strong increase in abundance of *G. truncatulinoides* in the central-
309 western Mediterranean during the Maunder to a deep water mixing induced by strong winds linked
310 to an Atmospheric blocking event. During Maunder, a rather persisting annual mixing is also
311 confirmed by the peak in frequency of *Orbulina* spp. (Fig. 2). In fact, this species in the sediment
312 trap data from Gulf of Lions (Rigual-Hernández et al., 2012) displays a maximum abundance during

313 the summer season and as suggested by Rohling et al. (2004) and Pujol and Vergnaud-Grazzini et al.,
314 (1995) the *Orbulina* species prevail only in the summer mixed layers. In addition, the antithetic
315 response between $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. ruber}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. bulloides}$ signals during the Maunder (Fig. 2), could suggest a
316 possible seasonal contrast, due to strong temperature/salinity difference respectively in winter/spring
317 and summer/autumn (Pujol and Vergnaud-Grazzini et al., 1995).

318 The increase in abundance of *T. quinqueloba* - *G. glutinata* gr. (Fig. 2), at the end of these solar
319 minima events, just before the following warm phases, and the antithetic distribution of *G. inflata*
320 and *G. truncatulinoides*, suggests relatively warm climate condition during spring/fall associated with
321 high fertility surface waters (Rigual-Hernández et al., 2012). This higher fertility could reflect
322 enhanced river runoff due to wetter conditions. This feature is also supported by pollen data from
323 Tyrrhenian Sea record (Di Rita et al., 2018) where a marked increase in *Glomus*, accompanied by
324 *Pseudischizaea*, indicating soil erosion and downwash (which is expected during a phase of general
325 deforestation), is associated with an increase in planktonic foraminifer *T. quinqueloba*, suggesting a
326 nutrient supply in sea surface water.

327 Our findings shows similar characteristics evidenced in this area from lacustrine sediment in Iberian
328 Peninsula (Martín-Puertas et al., 2008; 2010; Moreno et al., 2012; Sánchez-López et al., 2016).

329

330 5.1.6 Industrial Period

331 The lower boundary of the IP in the western Mediterranean Sea corresponds to light values in
332 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G. ruber}$ record and to an increase in abundance of warm water species *G. ruber* white variety,
333 associated with a decrease in percentage of *G. truncatulinoides* and *G. bulloides* (Fig. 2).

334 These planktonic foraminiferal patterns in the Gulf of Lions sediment trap data, suggest warm climate
335 conditions during summer (Rigual-Hernández et al., 2012). Several authors (i.e. Taricco et al., 2009;
336 Lirer et al., 2014; Margaritelli et al., 2016) point out that this warming trend results a general signal
337 in the central Mediterranean region.

338

339 5.2 Correlation between Mediterranean records

340 For the first time we provide the correlation among different regions of the Mediterranean Sea
341 during the last 2700 years. This effort permits to verify the synchronicity of climate events in land
342 and ocean in order to better understand global forcing within the Mediterranean region (Fig. 3).
343 The comparison between the marine records of Menorca basin (this study), central and south
344 Tyrrhenian Sea (Lirer et al., 2013, 2014; Margaritelli et al. 2016), Taranto Gulf, (Grauel et al., 2013),
345 Adriatic Sea (Piva et al., 2008), Israel (Schilman et al., 2001) and the north European continental ones
346 (Moberg et al., 2005; Hegerl et al., 2006, 2007; Mann et al., 2008; Ljungqvist et al., 2010; Pages 2k
347 Consortium 2013), allows to highlight a similar climate evolution at Mediterranean scale.
348 Notwithstanding differences in age model, we underline a general good agreement between the long
349 and short term climate oscillations in sea surface Mediterranean $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ records (Fig. 3) during the
350 last 2700 years.
351 The cooling phase at ca. 250 - 300 BCE corresponding to the Greek solar minimum is widely
352 recognised in all the investigated Mediterranean records by $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ signatures (Fig. 3), excluding
353 the Taranto Gulf as probably due to a regional overprint. The cooling event recorded by $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$
354 heavy values at ca. - 600 BCE in the study core (Menorca area) has been correlated to the Homeric
355 solar minimum (Fig. 3).
356 Between 220 and 800 BCE, the cold events Roman II, III and IV are well documented by $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$
357 signals of the western basins (Fig. 3) and result time equivalent to the solar minima activity as already
358 evidenced by Lirer et al. (2014) and Margaritelli et al. (2016) in the central Mediterranean Sea. In
359 addition, the observed correspondence between the Roman III event with the north hemisphere
360 continental temperature anomaly (Mann et al., 2008; and Ljungqvist et al., 2010) reveal a remarkable
361 connection between continental and marine climatic pattern.
362 In the upper part of the DA, the prominent cooling event corresponding to the Roman IV solar
363 minimum, marks the beginning of a progressive cooling trend that culminates during the LIA (Fig.
364 3). Trends to cool temperatures during the DA have been also reconstructed in the north Europe

365 continental records (PAGES 2K Consortium, 2013; McGregor et al., 2015; Büntgen et al., 2016). It
366 results to be almost synchronous with an increase in amplitude change in solar activity ($\Delta^{14}\text{C}$, Stuiver
367 et al., 1998) and progressive shift *vs* negative NAO index according to NAO index reconstruction of
368 Olsen et al., (2012) (Fig. 3).

369 The MCA was characterized by rather temperate climate conditions as documented by marine
370 (Schilman et al., 2001, Grauel et al., 2013; Lirer et al., 2014; McGregor et al., 2015; Cisneros et al.,
371 2016; Margaritelli et al., 2016) and terrestrial paleo - archives (Büntgen et al., 2016). During this
372 time period, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ records and foraminiferal data document mild climate conditions with a short
373 - term cold dry event (MCE) at ca. 1050 CE and also characterized by a arboreal vegetation decrease
374 in the central Tyrrhenian area (Moreno et al., 2012; Margaritelli et al., 2016; Di Rita et al., 2018).
375 The MCA period was coincident with the climax of many Mediterranean cultures. During the twelfth
376 century, the medieval Byzantine Empire goes through an important societal expansion, with
377 substantial agricultural productivity, intensive monetary exchange, demographic growth, and its pre
378 - eminent international political situation (Xoplaki et al., 2015).

379 The establishment of colder conditions in the climate system from ca. 1200 CE upwards characterized
380 the entire LIA as provided by temperature reconstructions (PAGES 2K Consortium, 2013; Cisneros
381 et al., 2016) and by abrupt oscillation in Mediterranean $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ records (Fig. 3). In addition, this
382 cooling trend results almost synchronous with a progressive shift *vs* negative NAO index (Trouet et
383 al., 2009; Olsen et al., 2012). Weak NAO index associated with Atlantic Blocking event during LIA
384 and in particular in the late part of Maunder cold event (Barriopedro et al., 2008), has been considered
385 by Margaritelli et al. (2016) and Di Rita et al. (2018, 2018a) as internal climate forcing to explain the
386 changes in planktonic foraminiferal assemblage and in pollen data, respectively. In addition, Sicre et
387 al. (2016) suggested persistent blocked regimes under a combined effect of weak NAO index with
388 negative East Atlantic pattern (EA) in the western Mediterranean. Furthermore, Josey et al. (2011)
389 suggest a major effect of the EA respect to the NAO in the eastern and western Mediterranean basin.

390 During the LIA, three distinct cooling events well documented in prominent heavy values in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G}$.
391 *ruber* signals of western and eastern Mediterranean Sea clearly resembled the Wolf, Sporer and
392 Maunder solar minima recorded in the $\Delta^{14}\text{C}$ solar oscillation (Stuiver et al., 1998) (Fig. 3). This
393 correlation between the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G}$. *ruber* signals and solar minima supports the influence of solar forcing
394 on the climate variability in the Mediterranean sea as already introduced in literature (Lirer et al.,
395 2014; Margaritelli et al., 2016). In addition, as recorded in the previous cold dry event at ca. 1050 CE
396 (MCE), a prominent decline in the forest cover in the central Tyrrhenian area is documented during
397 the Maunder event (Di Rita et al., 2018; 2018a).

398 These persistent cold climate conditions are also documented in several paintings of winter
399 landscapes showing the severe winter seasons in Europe (i.e., Brueghel 1601; Avercamp 1608) as
400 well in the maximum frequency of freezing of Venice Lagoon occurred between 1700 and 1850
401 (Camuffo and Enzi, 1995).

402 Available data for the last two centuries are not enough to have a clear picture for this time interval,
403 but few $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G}$.*ruber* data seem to suggest an inversion in climate vs warm conditions (Grauel et al.,
404 2013; Lirer et al., 2014; Margaritelli et al., 2016).

405

406 **6. Conclusions**

407 We present a 2700 years high - resolution paleoclimate reconstruction based on planktonic
408 foraminiferal and stable isotopic data measured on marine sediment cores from the Balearic
409 Promontory (central-western Mediterranean).

410 The results allow us to identify and characterize six intervals related to known cultural / climatic
411 phases: Balearic Bronze Age (base core –50 BCE); Roman Period (50 BCE – 500 CE); Dark Age
412 (500 CE – 850 CE); Medieval Climate Anomaly (850 CE - 1200 CE); Little Ice Age (1200 CE – 1825
413 CE) and Industrial Period (1825 CE – top core). The BA is characterized by the occurrence of cold
414 and warm water species documenting mild climate condition punctuated by two short cooling phases.
415 This interval predates the long - term cooling trend upwards documented by planktonic foraminiferal

416 curve. The RP was generally dominated by the of cold winter condition with high productivity in the
417 surface water masses. The DA shows an alternation of warm - humid and cold – warm - dry climatic
418 oscillations. The cold - dry phase, corresponding to the solar minimum Roman IV, marks the
419 beginning of a long - term cooling trend that terminates during the LIA. The MCA was characterized
420 by the co - occurrence of summer and winter foraminiferal species suggesting a general mild climatic
421 condition. This climate phase is interrupted at ca. 1050 CE by a distinct cold - dry event (MCE).
422 During the LIA, planktonic foraminiferal assemblage and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ signal are consistent with overall
423 cool climate conditions documenting three short - term cooling climatic oscillations related to Wolf,
424 Spörer and Maunder solar activity minima. In particular, the strong increase in abundance of
425 planktonic foraminifer *G. truncatulinoides* during Maunder, documents mixing water during winter
426 that could be related to an Atmospheric - blocking event. The warming interval during the IP is
427 documented by the progressive increase in abundance of warm water species *G. ruber* white variety.
428 The Mediterranean $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ framework documents remarkable similarity in the frequency of the
429 oscillations between different parts of the Mediterranean basin, suggesting a synchronous response
430 of marine system to past climate forcings, like the solar minima. In particular, from the DA upwards,
431 the marine and continental proxy records show an overall parallelism suggesting a progressive
432 cooling up to the Maunder event.

433

434 **Acknowledgments**

435 This research has been financially supported by the Project of Strategic Interest NextData PNR 2011-
436 2013 (www.nextdatapoint.it), RITMARE (www.ritmare.it), OPERA (CTM2013-48639-C2-1-R)
437 Consolider-Redes (CTM2014-59111-REDC) and ERC-Consolidator TIMED project. Mercè
438 Cisneros benefited from a fellowship of the University of Barcelona. This is ISMAR-CNR
439 contribution number 1907. IC thanks ICREA Academia program from the Catalan government.

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690

691 **Figure caption:**

692 Fig. 1 – Location map of the study area with the position of the composite core (red point). Black
693 arrows represent surface-water circulation: NC=North Current; BC=Balearic Current. Grey arrows
694 represent to deep-water circulation and the shadow area corresponds to the region where Western
695 Mediterranean Deep Water (WMDW) is formed.

696 Fig. 2 - Distribution in time domain of planktonic foraminiferal paleoclimatic curve, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ (this
697 work), $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.bulloides}$ (Cisneros et al., 2016), planktonic foraminifera, $\Delta^{14}\text{C}$ (Stuiver et al., 1998) with
698 the position of the climatic phases related to the composite multicore HER-MC-MR3.1A/3.3
699 (Balearic Bronze Age, Roman Period, Dark Age, Medieval Climate Anomaly, Little Ice Age and
700 Industrial Period).

701 Fig. 3 - Comparison in time domain between North Hemisphere mean temperatures reconstruction
702 from different authors [Moberg et al., 2005 (blue curve); Hegerl et al., 2006, 2007 (yellow curve);
703 Mann et al., 2008 (green curve); Ljungqvist et al., 2010 (red curve)], Temperature anomaly ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
704 (Pages 2k Consortium, 2013), $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ (‰ VPDB) of Menorca core (this study), $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ (‰

705 VPDB) of Gulf of Gaeta (Margaritelli et al., 2016), $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ (‰ VPDB) of Gulf of Salerno (Lirer
706 et al., 2013; 2014); $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ (‰ VPDB) of Gulf of Taranto (Grauel et al., 2013), $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.sacculifer}$ (‰
707 VPDB) of Adriatic Sea (Piva et al., 2008), $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ (‰ VPDB) of Israel (Schilman et al., 2001),
708 $\Delta^{14}\text{C}$ (Stuiver et al., 1998) and NAO index (black line by Olsen et al., 2012; blue line by Trouet et
709 al., 2009). The acronym MWE corresponds to Medieval Warm Event, and MCE to Medieval Cold.
710 The black arrows with ages represent the ages when this areas becomes part of the Roman Empire.
711 Tab.1 - Tie points used on both cores to make age models with their attendant errors. Uncertainties
712 correspond to the resolution of each age model on its respective core. Also absolute dates (AMS¹⁴C
713 and biostratigraphy based on planktonic foraminiferal assemblage) are indicated. Years are expressed
714 as Before Common Era (BCE) and Common Era (CE). For more details on age model construction,
715 see Cisneros et al. (2016).

Fig.2

Fig.3

Core	Composite depth (cm)	Method	Ages (years BCE/CE)		Age-uncertainties interval (years BCE/CE)	
MR3.1A	5-5.5	Mg/Ca	1627	CE	1545-1665	CE
	6.5-7		1400	CE	1350-1484	CE
	10-10.5		1050	CE	1021-1165	CE
	12.5-13		766	CE	597-824	CE
	13-13.5	Mn ICP-MS	597	CE	497-766	CE
	13.5-14	Mg/Ca	497	CE	433-597	CE
	15-16	Mn ICP-MS	254	CE	184-390	CE
	21-22	Mg/Ca	133	BCE	170 BCE-25	CE
	22-23	Mn ICP-MS	170	BCE	207 -133	BCE
	24-25		551	BCE	625-207	BCE
26-27	Mg/Ca	702	BCE	779-625	BCE	
MR3.3	0.5-1	<i>G. truncatulinoides</i> peak	1708	CE	1708-1728	CE
	3.5-4	AMS14C	1484	CE	1383-1484	CE
	6.5-7		1256	CE	1063-1256	CE
	12-12.5		989	CE	911-1085	CE
	16-17		497	CE	438-621	CE
	20-21		50	CE	88 BCE-107	CE
	24-25		388	BCE	388-214	BCE
	26-27	<i>G. quadrilobatus</i> top acme	702	BCE	798-702	BCE

Samples	Age (CE/BCE) Cisneros et al. (2016)	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ <i>G. ruber</i> vs VPDB	<i>G. bulloides</i>	<i>G. glutinata</i>	<i>G. ruber</i> pink	<i>G. ruber</i> white	<i>G. sacculifer</i>	<i>G. quadrilobatus</i>	<i>G. inflata</i>	<i>T. quinqueloba</i>	<i>G. siphoniphera</i>
HEMC-MR 3.1	1875.0	0.12	32	82	5	96	1	8	34	20	24
HEMC-MR 3.1	1830.0	-0.29	11	61	4	104		9	23	29	12
HEMC-MR 3.1	1808.0	0.46	15	44	13	80	1	4	34	40	22
HEMC-MR 3.1	1786.0	0.71	14	64	11	97		2	40	14	16
HEMC-MR 3.1	1764.0	0.61	14	80	6	102			23	36	47
HEMC-MR 3.3	1741.5	0.67	34	21	4	18		3	28	23	23
HEMC-MR 3.3	1708.0	0.27	42	13	3	23		2	23	10	19
HEMC-MR 3.3	1665.5	-0.54	46	13	3	39	1	7	22	28	12
HEMC-MR 3.3	1627.5	-0.13	33	9	1	42	3	2	19	31	27
HEMC-MR 3.3	1580.0	0.35	43	11	6	36	2	8	14	18	32
HEMC-MR 3.3	1545.0	0.30	34	14	4	38		1	21	48	12
HEMC-MR 3.3	1513.5	0.84	45	21	12	43	4		37	15	13
HEMC-MR 3.3	1484.0	0.34	51	24	8	47	2	1	39	16	20
HEMC-MR 3.3	1437.0	0.21	40	12	6	34		3	26	11	17
HEMC-MR 3.3	1400.3	-0.13	55	23	6	48		3	39	12	17
HEMC-MR 3.3	1375.0	0.21	49	13	10	38		1	40	17	23
HEMC-MR 3.3	1357.0	-0.50	32	19	9	28	1	8	29	11	37
HEMC-MR 3.3	1314.0	-0.29	46	14	6	40	2	9	20	38	17
HEMC-MR 3.3	1256.0	0.36	44	17	13	46		12	32	41	16
HEMC-MR 3.3	1245.8	-0.01	46	10	8	17		2	35	13	22
HEMC-MR 3.3	1235.5	0.28	56	18	10	50	1	11	26	17	30
HEMC-MR 3.3	1225.3	0.63	46	21	11	45	1	5	44	20	23
HEMC-MR 3.3	1215.0	0.50	30	2	4	32		1	28	12	25
HEMC-MR 3.3	1204.8	0.11	43	10	8	34		13	30	31	28
HEMC-MR 3.3	1192.9	-0.21	21	7	12	34	2	9	19	18	13
HEMC-MR 3.3	1165.0	-0.31	36	22	17	25		16	26	9	15
HEMC-MR 3.3	1079.6	0.18	37	13	9	31	1	4	27	21	13
HEMC-MR 3.3	1050.8	-0.63	55	9	18	46	1	12	47	24	33
HEMC-MR 3.3	1021.1	0.35	49	31	19	44		18	41	42	29
HEMC-MR 3.3	988.6	-0.09	53	4	6	52	7	3	25	4	32
HEMC-MR 3.3	882.2	-0.85	38	6	10	36	2	5	43	20	39
HEMC-MR 3.3	824.4	0.33	43	12	18	31	1	6	50	26	18
HEMC-MR 3.3	766.6	0.45	48	14	13	42	3	7	42	22	17
HEMC-MR 3.3	732.0	0.64	63	23	23	51	3	6	39	8	15
HEMC-MR 3.3	696.0	-0.16	60	17	18	42	8		34	12	14
HEMC-MR 3.3	596.5	-0.22	46	3	18	42	4	25	37	4	25
HEMC-MR 3.3	497.0	0.51	39	13	15	36	7	10	26		14
HEMC-MR 3.3	392.1	0.28	55	15	14	38		15	42	16	18
HEMC-MR 3.3	254.4	0.04	63	26	8	42		7	48	9	17
HEMC-MR 3.3	118.0	0.18	55	35	9	48		4	27	4	36
HEMC-MR 3.3	49.9	0.00	51	18	10	18		6	54	6	31
HEMC-MR 3.3	-43.0	0.52	44	5	13	46	4		50		27
HEMC-MR 3.3	-155.0	-0.27	50	12	9	32	1	3	61	16	59
HEMC-MR 3.3	-257.0	0.28	63	8	10	56		19	46	15	13
HEMC-MR 3.3	-388.0	-0.48	38	7	16	43	6	24	26		28
HEMC-MR 3.3	-551.0	0.41	69	8	6	54		18	46	25	18
HEMC-MR 3.3	-702.0	-0.18	60	19	16	36	35	48	59	22	30

<i>Orbulina</i> spp.	<i>N.pachyderma</i> sx	<i>N.pachyderma</i> dx	<i>G.truncatulinoides</i> dx	<i>G.truncatulinoides</i> sx	<i>N.dutertrei</i>	<i>Clavatorella</i> spp.	TOT planctonici
42		55	2	30			399
26		31		25		2	324
33		25		37			333
21		51		39		3	358
24		18		46			382
48		8		39	12		227
36		4		44	7		184
42		6		33	15	1	222
36		5		20	16		211
58		9		25	21		240
26		6		27	22	2	221
18		7		36	32		238
38		5		32	28		260
37		13		20	16		195
29		10		28	12		227
41		4		31	27	2	247
31		12		28	27		240
18		6		18	20	2	210
22		10		21	33		263
19		5		30	25		186
18		21		23	16		241
20		17		26	33		266
42		8		32	19		205
52		17		42	20		285
43		5		26	11		199
41		35		39	5		250
32		14		18	8		191
29		16		51	32		318
34		5		28	15		306
36				51	9	3	229
21		2		35	9		228
32		2		28	17	3	244
25		5		21	14		225
53		6		42	11		280
47		7		38	16		253
36		18		44	19		275
44		11		35	13		224
36		16		45	21		276
32		11		49	13		262
35		12		27	7		244
44		9		30	8		234
49		8		31	8		241
54		2		61	32		342
41		5		35	30		278
45				28	9		232
32		7		52	13		279
36		4		23	33		361